

Polarographic Examination of Active Components of *Datura stramonium*

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The polarograms, the limiting current- pH , $E_{1/2}$ - pH , limiting current-concentration and slopes of $\log \bar{i}$ vs $\log h$ plots of the principal component of *Datura stramonium* stem-, leaf- and root-extracts in cold 1% $HClO_4$ solution prove the catalytic nature of limiting currents, similar to those of atropine. From the calibration curve (limiting current-concentration) of atropine sulphate at pH 5.3 the air-dried stems, leaves and roots of the plant are found to contain respectively 1.10, 1.05 and 1.04% of atropine.

POLAROGRAPHY together with chromatography offers the most rapid and sensitive analytical technique for purposes of identification, estimation and establishment of the course of electro-reduction (or -oxidation) of organic compounds present as active principles in medicinal plants¹. Organic compounds present in these plants exhibit different behaviour at dropping mercury electrode depending upon their chemical nature.

The plant under present investigation, *Datura stramonium* (family : Solanaceae) contains an alkaloid, atropine which is well known for its wide therapeutic value^{2,3}. The present work has been carried out in order to establish a routine polarographic method for the estimation of atropine in various parts of the plant.

Experimental

Polarograms were recorded (298 K) with a radiometer pen-recording polarograph, Polariter PO4. A Kaloušek cell with a saturated calomel electrode (scc) was used as the reference electrode. The dropping mercury electrode (dme) made from sargent capillary was used having the following characteristics : $m=0.952 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t=4.3 \text{ s}$ at 60 cm height of mercury reservoir in 0.5 mol dm^{-3} KCl solution at zero applied potential (scc). The pH values of the solutions were measured before and after recording each polarogram on ELICO LI-10 pH meter with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \text{ pH}$ unit.

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. The stems, leaves and roots of the plant *Datura stramonium* were collected in July-August, separately dried in air, crushed and 40.0 g of each kept immersed in 1% perchloric acid (400 ml) for a week at room temperature and the cold extracts filtered before use. Each extract was diluted 1000 times with conductivity water after adding tetramethylammonium acetate-borate buffer (0.075 mol dm^{-3} , final strength) and tetramethylammonium bromide

(0.1 mol dm^{-3} , final concentration) for obtaining the test solutions.

Results and Discussion

Polarograms of *Datura* stem-extract at different pH values exhibit single waves with their heights decreasing with increasing pH values (Fig. 1). The current- pH plot (Fig. 5) shows an exponential

Fig. 1. pH -dependence of polarograms of *Datura* stem-extract (0.01 ml of 1% $HClO_4$ solution made up to 10 ml of test solution).

decrease of limiting current, reminiscent of an acid-base equilibrium in which the acidic component alone is electro-active. Such a behaviour is usually exhibited by catalytic hydrogen waves^{4,5}. Dependence of limiting current on concentration (in terms of dilution of the extract from 1000 to 31.25) exhibits Langmuir-type behaviour, a characteristic of catalytic waves⁶. The nature of the polarographic waves has been verified by the slopes of $\log \bar{i}$ vs $\log h$ plots over the entire wave at two pH 's 5.3 and 8.4. The slopes range from -1.09 at 1.48V to -0.16 at 1.70V and from -0.39 at 1.52V to -0.21 at 1.82V at pH 's 5.3 and 8.4, respectively. Polarograms of cold and diluted extracts of *Datura* leaves and roots at different pH values under the identical conditions as employed above show similar decrease in limiting currents with increasing pH values (Figs. 2 and 3). The current- pH , $E_{1/2}$ - pH

and current-concentration plots are similar to those of the stem-extract, indicating similar nature of the active components present in the stems, leaves and roots of *Datura stramonium*. The $\log \bar{i}$ vs $\log h$

the active component of the extracts of *Datura* stems, leaves and roots with atropine. Mixed polarogram of atropine sulphate and each extract (1 : 1) at pH 7.2 show single waves with enhanced current supporting the above conclusion.

Fig. 2. pH-dependence of polarograms of *Datura* leaf-extract (0.01 ml of 1% HClO₄ solution made up to 10 ml of test solution).

Fig. 3. pH-dependence of polarograms of *Datura* root-extract (0.01 ml of 1% HClO₄ solution made up to 10 ml of test solution).

plots for the waves of leaf-extract have similar slope values ranging from -1.09 to -0.17 at pH 5.3 and from -0.36 to -0.20 at pH 8.4. The corresponding slopes for the root-extract range from -1.09 to -0.17 and from -0.40 to -0.23 at pH's 5.3 and 8.4, respectively.

The polarograms (Fig. 4) of atropine sulphate (0.1 mol m⁻³) at different pH values and similar ionic strengths and buffer concentrations as employed for the extracts show striking resemblance (Figs. 1-3). The plots of current pH, (Fig. 5), $E_{1/2}$ -pH (Fig. 6), current-concentration (Fig. 7) and slope values of $\log \bar{i}$ vs $\log h$ plots for the waves at

Fig. 4. pH-dependence of polarograms of atropine sulphate (0.1 mol m⁻³).

pH 5.3 and 8.4 (-1.08 to -0.16 for pH 5.3 and from -0.40 to -0.25 for pH 8.4) confirm the catalytic nature of the polarographic waves and identity of

Fig. 5. Dependence of limiting current on pH: (○) atropine sulphate (0.1 mol m⁻³), (●) stem-extract (0.001 ml), (Δ) leaf-extract (0.001 ml) and (□) root-extract (0.001 ml).

Fig. 6. Dependence of half-wave potential on pH: (○) atropine sulphate (0.1 mol m⁻³), (●) stem-extract (0.001 ml), (Δ) leaf-extract (0.001 ml) and (□) root-extract (0.001 ml).

To determine the concentration of atropine in different parts of *Datura*, polarograms for different concentrations (0.1-1.7 mol m⁻³) of atropine sulphate (pH 5.3) have been recorded. The calibration curve (i_{lim} vs concentration plot) has the slope of 3.28 μA mmol⁻¹. The concentration of atropine in air-dried stems, leaves and roots of *Datura stramonium* have thus, been estimated to be 1.10, 1.05 and 1.04%, respectively.

Fig. 7. Concentration (in terms of dilution) dependence of limiting currents at pH 5.3: (O) stem-extract, (●) leaf-extract and (Δ) root-extract.

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